

FORMING A SENSE OF NATIONAL PRIDE IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article discusses the role of the nation's national-spiritual outlook, customs, traditions, manners, lifestyle, and high spirituality in the formation of students' sense of national pride.

Key words: national pride, sense of national pride, national independence, national pride, perfection.

The unique position of a particular nation in the world community and its possession does not depend on its large number or small number. On the contrary, the ability to show national characteristics, the deep understanding of the rights of the representatives of the nation, not to be materially and morally dependent on other nations, and to exist independently determines its status in the international arena. .

To be able to boldly express one's views on international relations, to fight to increase the honor and reputation of the nation, to prevent the formation of negative attitudes towards oneself in other nations, and to further increase the prestige of the nation.

The reality of life indicates that all the knowledge and experiences, words, concepts, imagination and conclusions in the world are directly or indirectly related to human activity, develop, enrich, improve, or vice versa - become obsolete, pass their life, will face trouble. At this moment there is such a great phenomenon that as long as there is a conscious life of mankind, there will never be suffering. A person who lives with a sense of national pride in his heart is a healthy thinker, lives with noble dreams and is always appreciated by the society.

In the words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, "We will continue to give priority to this issue, which is the most important for us, and we will do all the necessary work to support the activities of national cultural centers in a practical way." ", "I would like to emphasize that if anyone thinks that the issue of spirituality is only the work of the Center of Spirituality or relevant ministries and agencies, they are making a big mistake. This is our country and society, all leaders, our advanced intellectuals, who are our mountain of faith, is the most important and important task of all of us.¹

Based on the above thoughts of the President, it should be emphasized that instilling the sense of national pride in students, including the younger generation, begins with kindergarten, school, higher education institution, and family. The main participants in the formation of a sense of national pride in the family are parents and family leaders. .

National pride is a concept that expresses a feeling of pride in a nation's material or spiritual achievement, success. It shows one of the aspects of human spiritual maturity. National pride is unlimited respect and respect for all the material and spiritual wealth, historical heritage, customs, traditions, manners, lifestyle, and high spirituality of all the historical achievements

¹ Ш.М.Мирзиёев. Янги Ўзбекистон стратегияси. – Тошкент, 2021 й. Б –313

and lessons of our people created over the centuries. A relationship with someone is a concept that represents foster care.

People who do not care about the future of nations, who do not know, do not value, and forget their national identity, their history, national abilities, language, and interests, do not have national pride, pride in the nation, and nationalism. We cannot call such people spiritually perfect people. Restoring and growing national pride is one of the priority tasks in our spiritual life. It is human nature to associate oneself with a certain social group, stratum, category, nation, state, region, period or dynasty. Therefore, it is a natural and spiritual phenomenon for a person to be happy with the achievements of his people, nation and state, and strive to leave it to the next generation to enrich it again.

Due to the renewal of the society in the period of the fundamental turning point of the historical development of peoples and nations, the restoration and growth of national pride is directly related to the construction of national statehood. Bringing national spiritual and cultural values to the minds and hearts of young people in detail, feeding them with the spiritual wealth created by their ancestors, restoring and growing national pride is done by studying, understanding and appreciating the history of this nation. The national pride in the life of the Uzbek people is enhanced by studying the life and fate of the great people of their nation. Another task of national pride is to unite the people, the nation, to advance towards a higher goal. Every person living in this country needs to deeply understand that achieving our noble goal, taking our rightful place on the world scale, and protecting the independence of our country depends primarily on us, on our own opportunities and potential, and on our determination. In this regard, along with political, military, economic factors, the sense of national pride is also an important criterion. National pride is such a great power that relying on this power in history, many peoples have survived the most difficult challenges and managed to build a free and prosperous life that arouses the desire for it.²

It is not for nothing that the ideas of national peace, development of the country and national well-being take the leading place in the minds of our people and the ideology of our society. National pride should be the foundation of all our work. Irrespective of nationality and nationality, instilling these holy ideas into the life and consciousness of every person living in this country, in this land, should become the biggest support and confidence for each of us.

By breaking the sense of national pride in students, strengthening faith and belief, strengthening their will, and educating them as well-rounded people with their own independent opinion. Instilling in their thinking the virtue of not forgetting oneself, preserving and respecting the sacred qualities of their forefathers, and making them live with pride and pride as "I am an Uzbek child".

National pride is national pride. National pride is a nation's conscious awareness that it is a single social unit. This is such a strong state of mind, thanks to which historical unity, blood kinship, language, culture, spirituality, economic life and future unity take a deep place in the hearts of the representatives of the nation.

The feeling of national pride has a cultural, spiritual, social and humanitarian content. Because of this, it creates conditions for meeting the spiritual needs of all peoples in independent

² Маънавият асосий тушунчалар луғати, Республика маънавият ва марифат маркази Ўзбекистон файласуфлари миллий жамияти, – Тошкент, 2021. – Б.403.

Uzbekistan. For this reason, only people who have national pride in their hearts can be the means to ensure inter-ethnic harmony for the prosperity of our country.

In the process of social and cultural development, a person creatively transforms, modernizes, enriches and assimilates the national pride and abilities of his ancestors. Therefore, by breaking the legacy of our ancestors into the minds of students, we protect young people from the threat of other foreign ideas and enrich the minds of students with innovative ideas that are suitable for today's times. The future of the country, which has generations brought up with such ideas, which serve for the development and future of our country and contribute to its prosperity, will certainly be great.

National pride includes all aspects of the nation's spiritual maturity, heritage and present-day values. As the economic and spiritual achievements that have been achieved and will be achieved as a result of national independence increase, the feeling of pride in Uzbekistan - national pride - will increase. National pride belongs equally to all citizens of our country, and all citizens are equally responsible for its growth.

National pride is an important condition that guarantees self-awareness, independence, and freedom of different peoples and nations. Therefore, the realization of national identity determines the place and status of this nation in the society of individuals. Having a sense of national pride and pride is a solid basis for understanding the identity of each nation. As we dwell on the incomparable role of national pride in the education of today's growing youth, we recall the words of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, "The sense of national pride is for a person it is natural, because it is inherited from the parents and is expressed from the first word that the child says to his parents, to the whole world. Without cultivating love and respect for one's people, their traditions, language and culture, it is impossible to educate a real person who perceives one's people as one of the equals in the whole global community of nations, a lover of one's Motherland.

The ideology of the national perspective includes patriotism formed on the basis of national pride values, feelings of unity, solidarity and tolerance. The stronger the love and pride of young people for the motherland, the deeper the understanding of the history, mother tongue, culture, customs, traditions and abilities of each person of the motherland, the stronger and more stable independence will be.

At present, the issue of strengthening of independence, formation of personal spirituality in confidently moving towards the future is one of the main directions. National consciousness, language and culture play a leading role in the restoration and development of the nation's spirituality. Their effective use serves to develop national feelings, pride and pride in students, and to form a sense of national identity.

By feeling a sense of national pride and pride, students are able to understand their belonging to a certain nation and their ethno-psychological characteristics, and to be proud of their nation's contribution to world civilization and to feel loyalty to the nation to which they belong. It causes the awakening of feelings, which causes the students to become well-rounded individuals.

The views of the great scholars who lived and created in Central Asia on personal development are an important basis for world education at the modern stage. Harmonization of national pedagogic abilities with democratic abilities in the existing conditions, breaking humanistic and democratic ideas into the content of education, applying advanced technologies to the educational process, and increasing the effectiveness of education is the

demand of the time. That is why the Republic of Uzbekistan, after gaining the status of an independent state, pays special attention to the training of personnel suitable for a humane society.

In the works of our ancestors, issues such as national and spiritual values, their socio-spiritual significance, historical approach to them, the content of practical actions taken to restore national values in the years of independence, and the manifestation of feelings of national pride in the individual. has found its expression.

Several scientists have written about the socio-philosophical aspects of the development of spiritual and moral qualities in the person's maturity, the realization of the national identity in the person, the formation of feelings of national pride and pride, and the role of national spirituality in the process. emphasized.

Thorough knowledge of the history of the Uzbek people, a correct understanding of the essence of historical processes, a conscious attitude to social events, learning from the activities of national heroes will help students to have a sense of national pride. History should be able to reflect the sense of understanding the past, as the first goal in forming students' sense of national pride. In this way, the past, history of the nation and its place in the history of world development become important. Here, not only history, but also national-spiritual heritage, in particular, folk art, national customs, ceremonies and traditions have an impact on national education in forming a sense of national pride in students.

National pride is a socio-psychological phenomenon, and the possession of a sense of national pride is a spiritual and moral quality, which is formed in the process of effectively organized social education. A person's spiritual and moral maturity, level of education, worldview, and active attitude to the socio-historical process play an important role in having a sense of national pride.

Therefore, it is of urgent importance to analyze the specialization directions and activity content of students, to determine their pedagogical capabilities based on their activities, and at the same time, to develop the theoretical and practical foundations of forming a sense of national pride in students by studying the characteristics of academic subjects. . Because future specialists with a high sense of national pride will be able to make a worthy contribution to strengthening the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In order to form a sense of national pride in students, it is permissible to start breaking this feeling not only in higher education institutions, but also in the family. The factors of national pride would not have been damaged by this process.

Figure 1. Factors of formation of national pride.

The role of the family in education in the spirit of national pride is incomparable. First of all, this is seen in the growing role of family and child education in the conditions of national independence. Without creating a healthy environment in the family, without deciding on a new way of life, it is impossible to bring up new thinking children, or rather, a new generation. The young generation, brought up in the spirit of national pride, matures in accordance with the future in modern conditions based on such cultural and experimental processes.

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